

Dewa Sanzan

also known as “The Three Sacred Mountains of Dewa”

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Entry tags: Temple, Japonic, Shrines, Religious Group, Shintō, Japanesic, Japan, Japanese, Language, Sect Shintō, Shrine Shintō, Religious Place, Yamagata Prefecture, Shrine

The Dewa Sanzan (The Three Mountains of Dewa) are three sacred mountains in Japan's Yamagata Prefecture that are important sites in the history of the ascetic mountain faith known as Shugendō. Their name comes from their location in what was once the old imperial province of Dewa. Today, they are divided between Tsuruoka City and the town of Shōnai. The trio of peaks—Mt. Haguro, Mt. Yudono, and Mt. Gassan—have for centuries been a site of pilgrimage for a variety of religious traditions including Shintō, Buddhism, and Shugendō. The site's foundation is ascribed to Prince Hachiko, a sixth century imperial prince who escaped north to Dewa after his father Emperor Sushun's assassination. The mountains' first written attestation as a site of pilgrimage is dated to 1209 in the Kamakura period (1185-1333). Located in Japan's far northern region of Tohoku and thus at a distance from the imperial capital, Dewa Sanzan was difficult to visit before modern transportation eased the journey, which cemented the idea of the mountains as located somewhere far beyond the mundane world. The three peaks are the center of the Haguro sect of Shugendō, a syncretic tradition that blends Shinto, Buddhism, and older forms of mountain worship. According to the Haguro sect, Mt. Haguro represents birth, Mt. Gassan represents death, and Mt. Yudono represents rebirth. Yamabushi (“those hidden in the mountains”), the sect's ascetic adherents, train by braving extremes in the elements and meditating under waterfalls or while hanging off of cliffs, among other practices. By traversing between the peaks, the yamabushi ritually traversed between birth, death, and rebirth. The sect once hosted four yearly major rituals—one for each season—and today, all save for the Spring Peak (Haru no Mine) ritual survive. Lay visitors have also performed pilgrimage to the mountains for centuries; one famous Edo period visitor was the poet Matsuo Bashō, who describes his visit in the travelogue *Oku no Hosomichi*. Despite the Dewa Sanzan's religious position being shaken up by the 1870s government-imposed, locally undesired divestment of Shinto from Buddhism (*shinbutsu bunri*), some physical remnants of the earlier heavily syncretized era still survive. A particularly visible example of this is the five-story pagoda at what used to be the temple of Jakkō-ji but is now called Ideha Shrine. The former temple is now a shrine because of the Meiji coopting of the sites and rituals solely for Shinto. Since Shugendō's reestablishment in the late 1940s under the postwar Japanese constitution, the peaks survive as a site of pilgrimage and training for the Haguro sect. As scholar Gaynor Sekimori observes, “Shugendō seems to have found a firm place in modern religious practice, but it is highly unlikely that its institutional forms, destroyed at Meiji, will ever be recreated at Hagurosan.” But the Dewa Sanzan survive, both in a religious capacity as well as a major attraction for local tourism.

Date Range: 592 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Western Yamagata Prefecture and the Sea of Japan Coast

Region tags: Yamagata Prefecture, Honshu, Japan

The Sea of Japan coast of Yamagata Prefecture including the Three Mountains of Dewa

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Carmen Blacker. *The Catalpa Bow: A Study of Shamanistic Practices in Japan*. (Surrey: Japan Library, 1999)
- Source 2: Frank Clements. "The Fall Peak, Professional Culture, and Document Production in Early Modern Haguro Shugendō." *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies*, Vol. 46, No. 2 (2019), pp. 219-246.
- Source 3: H. Byron Earhart. "Four Ritual Periods of Haguro Shugendō in Northeastern Japan." *History of Religions*, Vol. 5, No. 1 (Summer, 1965), pp. 93-113.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://nirc.nanzan-u.ac.jp/journal/6/issue/171/article/1176>
- Source 1 Description: Gaynor Sekimori. "Paper Fowl and Wooden Fish: The Separation of Kami and Buddha Worship in Haguro Shugendō, 1869-1875." *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies* 32/2: 197-234.
- Source 2 URL: <https://dewasanzan.com/about/>
- Source 2 Description: Timothy Bunting. "The Dewa Sanzan: An Introduction."
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.dewasanzan.jp/publics/index/10/>
- Source 3 Description: Dewa Sanzan Jinja. "Jinja no Sairei."

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Reference: Haguro Tourist Association. "Dewa sanzan museum of history". Haguro Tourist Association. Accessed April 29, 2024. <https://hagurokanko.jp/en/facility/dewasanzanrekishihakubutsukan/>.

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Most famously, hundreds of bronze mirrors were excavated from the "Mirror Pond" (Kagami-ike) on Mount Haguro. A number of them are held by the Tokyo National Museum and the Dewa Sanzan Museum of History.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The Three Mountains are Mt. Haguro (Hagurosan), Mt. Yudono (Yudonosan), and Mt. Gassan (Gassan).

– Tree, grove, or forest

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: Religious structures

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Tsuruoka City and the town of Shōnai.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: In premodern times, there were pilgrimage routes to the sacred mountains. In contemporary Japan, there are several prefectural highways, trains, and Japan National Route 47.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Several temple and shrine buildings, as well as a museum (formerly a treasure house) and pagoda

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: All three peaks and the religious sites on them are part of one broader entity collectively known as Dewa Sanzan.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Tourism

Notes: Dewa Sanzan is a famous heritage site and also a popular hiking destination.

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Pilgrimage groups often worship communally at Dewa Sanzan, but individual worship is also performed.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Some parts torn down

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

Notes: It was partially destroyed and later heavily modified because of the Boshin War and the Meiji era divestment of Shinto and Buddhism.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

Notes: Structures have burned down in the past.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Due to the presence and activity of multiple religious traditions at Dewa Sanzan, including Shugendo, Shinto, and Buddhism, the sites in the mountains were dedicated to many different supernatural beings such as buddhas and kami.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Mt. Gassan, as the peak associated with the past and death, has particularly been considered as a place where one may commune with or worship the spirits of ancestors, though the divine status of these spirits is unclear.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Imperial Prince

Notes: According to legend, Prince Hachiko, the son of Emperor Sujin, founded the first religious sites at Dewa Sanzan beginning in 593.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

- Priests
- Corvee labourers
- Specialized labourers/craftspeople
- Other [specify]: There were generations upon generations of construction and remodeling at this site; the range of people involved would be wide

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

- Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: three-legged crow (yatagarasu) and bodhisattva Kannon

Notes: According to legend, Prince Hachiko was led to Mt. Haguro by a three-legged crow and encountered there the bodhisattva of mercy/compassion, Kannon.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

- Other [specify]: An imperial prince's escape northward from the capital of Kyoto and his encounter with a bodhisattva

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Various features of the mountains' geography, including cliffs, caves, and waterfalls

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: yes, several buildings are connected as part of complexes of temples and shrines

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: Because there are multiple religious traditions at the site, there are various systems of hierarchies according to each.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: n/a

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: concrete, metal

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are many statues of buddhas, bodhisattvas, deities, and dragons etc. throughout the Dewa Sanzan.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There is a statue on Mt. Haguro of En no Gyoja, considered to be the founder of Shugendo.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: n/a

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Images of dragons and other supernatural beings/creatures, flora/fauna, and other religious motifs are carved in relief from the wood on several temples and shrines.

- ↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - No
 - ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are paintings of buddhas, bodhisattvas, and other deities.
 - ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For example, there is a painting of Prince Hachiko/Nojo
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– I don't know

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: n/a

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Dragons and lion-dogs, if they can be considered zoomorphic

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Notes: Although an argument could be made for the mountains themselves being geomorphic supernatural beings that are then depicted.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– I don't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– No

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Human narratives
– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: However, there is a grave dedicated to Prince Hachiko at Hachiko Shrine.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: There are many deities worshipped at Dewa Sanzan.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: This seems likely given narratives concerning Mt. Gassan and, for example, stories about reincarnation as in the case of Date Masamune's mother's dream the night he was conceived. According to the Date clan's orthodox history, Date Chike Kiroku, Masamune's mother, Lady Yoshi, commissioned a Dewa ascetic named Chōkai, to offer prayers at Yudonosan for her to bear a child. After setting up the purification wand returned by Chōkai as proof of his pilgrimage, Yoshi had a dream in which a white-bearded monk asked if he could borrow her womb in order to be reborn.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

In dreams:

– Yes

In trance possession:

– I don't know

Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Tengu are associated with ascetic practices in Japan

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: n/a

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: N/A

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: One could make an argument that the various supernatural beings worshipped at Dewa Sanzan monitor the activities there.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: I don't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Seasonal

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, yamabushi practices must be done a particular way

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Notes: is a goma a sacrifice?

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Material offerings are not explicitly mandatory but are considered normative.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Attendance is not mandatory for lay visitors but may be mandatory or heavily assumed/emphasized for religious specialists.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: n/a

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– Yes

↳ Birth
– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood
– No

↳ Death
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Rebirth

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Seasonal

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Shrines and temples are typically open during festivals in Japan, but ascetic practices and major ritual events typically require a level of initiation.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: I don't know

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Notes: However, Shinto rituals often include a symbolic feasting or commensal communion between kami and humans called 'naorai.'

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Notes: Details of divinatory practices are scarce and close guarded as secret within esoteric Buddhism and Shugendo.

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– I don't know

Notes: Unlikely

↳ Divination through human communication:

– I don't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– I don't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Smoke
– Flame
Notes: As in goma rituals

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Yamabushi rituals

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Yamabushi are known to develop healing powers from their training at sacred mountains such as Dewa Sanzan. There are also narratives of miraculous healing at sites at Dewa Sanzan.

↳ Incubation
– No

↳ Healing magic
– Yes

↳ Cleansing
– Yes
Notes: Ritual purification could be considered an act of cleansing.

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
– No

↳ Expiation
– Yes
Notes: Goma ceremonies might be considered a form of expiation.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

Notes: The answer depends on the time period. Historically, there have been barriers to women serving as religious specialists at Dewa Sanzan in Buddhism, Shinto, and Shugendo, as well as lay women entering the mountains. However, today women may serve as Shinto priests and shrine maidens (unknown if women currently serve as priests at the shrines in the mountains) and conduct women-only yamabushi training at certain times in certain places.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Historically they were all Japanese, today there are foreign yamabushi

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: No, yamabushi wander by definition.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when you train on the Three Mountains, you live there, at least temporarily.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Scripture might be written or copied (such as the Heart Sūtra) here. However, emphasis is often on oral and embodied practices.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes ascetic practices are transmitted orally.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: See above for the legend of Prince Hachiko.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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